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1. Introduction

Within the research lines of Spoke 4, one of our main goals is to experiment with the use of virtual (energy-efficient) technologies within defined and representative real-case scenarios. In particular, we aim to experiment with them using different museum and art collection templates to design specific case studies, deriving and applying best practices that can be further adapted and reused in institutions and contexts with similar characteristics. The six templates of museums and art collections identified are described as follows:

- Type A – high-density and innovative museum;
- Type B – natural history and scientific museum;
- Type C – widespread art gallery;
- Type D – sites museums with tangible and intangible heritage and landscapes, among those that have either low or no virtual and digital implementations with a particular focus in southern Italy;
- Type E – historical palaces, labelled as museums, among the most important in the Italian heritage context, including UNESCO sites;
- Type F – demo-ethnic-anthropological museums, including rural culture museums (with less than 20,000 visitors per year), anthropological museums and museums of art and popular traditions.

In this deliverable, we describe the outcomes of the work conducted with the cultural heritage institutions we have contacted that are compliant with Type D, with whom we have established collaborative research projects. In particular, we have identified a set of cultural institutions with which we have set up specific research projects to put into practice existing and ad-hoc tools developed to provide a system to be freely reusable in a similar context by other cultural institutions not necessarily involved in the project.

Some of these projects, referred to as “core” case studies, have been conducted in collaboration with companies that provide implementation efforts and institutions that offer domain-specific cultural knowledge and citizen engagement. The companies involved were selected through a public call for applications, supported by the project's funds (i.e., cascade calls). These “core” case studies have also been accompanied by additional *research case studies* aligned with the project templates and goals, which the partners of Spoke 4 have used to experiment with further adoptions of the aforementioned workflow, methodologies and tools within the project's period.

2. "Core" case studies

2.1. VITALE: The «Carlo Levi» literary park: a valorization project through a virtual technologies

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

The idea of Literary Parks originated in the late 1980s through the initiative of the Ippolito Nievo Foundation. However, its practical implementation as a strategy for local territorial development took shape thanks to the impetus provided by the European Union. Within the framework of Italy's Community Support Framework (CSF) Objective 1, programming cycle 1994/99, axis 3.1 "Incentives for Tourism Investments," the EU approved the Global Grant titled "Literary Parks". In the summer of 2009, the establishment and coordination of I Parchi Letterari® were entrusted to Paesaggio Culturale Italiano Srl, a company created to promote the Parks and related initiatives. Its aim was to position them as destinations for a specific type of tourism—cultural, sustainable, and responsible—that could offer concrete development opportunities for local communities and businesses within a functional and efficient national network.

The Literary Park dedicated to Carlo Levi (1902–1975) pays tribute to the painter, writer, and doctor from Turin who, between 1935 and 1936, was exiled by the Fascist regime to a small village in Lucania, Aliano. From that experience came *Cristo si è fermato a Eboli* (1945), a literary and anthropological work that transformed Aliano into a symbol of resistance to Fascism and the marginalization of Southern Italy.

As part of the CHANGES project, the goal is to renew these two parks, enhancing their landscape and cultural heritage with new digital technologies, while paying special attention to environmental sustainability, social inclusion, and respect for territorial, linguistic, and cultural diversity.

At the beginning of 2023, the cultural offerings related to the Parco Letterario "Carlo Levi" – integrated within the historic center of Aliano – were particularly rich. In addition to a series of plaques affixed to the walls and inspired by the places of *Cristo si è fermato ad Eboli* (1945), there were several museums connected either directly (Pinacoteca Carlo Levi, Casa di Confino Carlo Levi, Museo della Fotografia) or indirectly (Museo Civiltà Contadina and the Museo delle Maschere, then being set up) to Carlo Levi's Aliano experience. Despite this wealth, two significant shortcomings were evident: the limited opening of the sites (due to a shortage of staff) and the lack of technology (no digital or even printed resources were available to visitors).

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

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In order to enhance the cultural heritage and the territory of literary parks, and in the specific case of the Carlo Levi park, it was decided to carry out a digitization phase (photos, videos, 360 images, and 3D models) of the assets and locations. This would provide a working basis for producing virtual tours and digital containers to be used to disseminate knowledge of the park. To achieve this, techniques for producing 3D models (such as NERF) were initially studied, which did not require the use of complex and expensive tools, but only a simple PC and photos. Subsequently, NERF was used to study and ultimately select and apply the more recent technique, Gaussian splatting, which, in addition to not requiring laser scanning like NERF, also does not require any special hardware (e.g., Nvidia PC cards like NERF).

For the visualization and manipulation of the models obtained with these techniques, the open-source framework ATON was chosen due to its efficiency and flexibility in displaying 3D models, particularly in the standard "glTF" format, which also included the original 360° images. All this made it possible to create interactive 3D environments where multimedia content can be displayed and, starting from various immersive environments, also to build interactive virtual tours.

All the immersive environments and content were then inserted into digital containers such as maps, galleries, and guided tour applications for use via touchscreens or mobile devices. Everything created will be accessible through integrated touchscreen applications and smartphone apps. Therefore, the main technologies used were 3D visualization and 360° immersive content created with the ATON and Three.js frameworks, which allow real-time rendering of three-dimensional models and panoramic images directly in web browsers without the need for plugins or additional software. This ATON-based content was used to build immersive tours.

The system components are therefore divided into some main layers, each with a well-defined technical role:

- **Core Layer – Immersive and 3D Content Management** At the heart of the system is a custom instance of ATON.js, integrated with Node.js, the Three.js graphics engine. This layer serves as a repository and distribution engine for 3D models (glTF/GLB, OBJ, PLY formats), enriched with multimedia hotspots and interactive tours.
- **Local Usage Layer – Touchscreen Interface** The local layer is a web application for kiosks and interactive screens, developed with HTML5, CSS3, JavaScript, and Leaflet. This interface, optimized for touch use and timeout management, is the main onsite access point, serving as a multimedia container and integrating the map created by an external vendor.
- **Remote Access Layer – Mobile PWAs** Three Progressive Web Applications were developed for remote access: Additionally, 3D models and 360° photos

(complementing those initially carried out by Engineering) were created, documenting Levi's locations and objects, high-definition surveys, and interviews to be integrated as content within tours and digital galleries.

NAIS S.r.l. has implemented the following technologies:

- An interactive web mapping platform using Leaflet library for rendering OpenStreetMap data, providing an intuitive geographical interface for navigating the Aliano locations and seamlessly integrating the virtual tours within the map environment.
- 3D visualization and immersive 360° content delivery through ATON.js and Three.js frameworks, enabling real-time rendering of three-dimensional models and panoramic imagery within web browsers without requiring additional plugins or software installations.
- A progressive Web Application (PWA) architecture developed using HTML5, CSS3, and JavaScript ES6+, ensuring cross-platform compatibility and optimal performance across desktop and mobile devices while providing offline functionality capabilities.

An advanced AI-powered artwork recognition system for the Talking Paintings features, implementing a sophisticated three-stage visual recognition pipeline using deep learning models optimized for mobile deployment:

- Forum Engineering Srl adopted the following technologies:
- 360° images (Insta 360 Pro): plaques and some points of interest.
- 3D reconstructions (laser scanner): Carlo Levi Art Gallery, House of Exile, Piazza del Belvedere.
- 3D models (photogrammetry): bronze bust of Carlo Levi.
- High-resolution digital reproductions: artworks (Aliano, Rome).
- High-resolution digital reproductions: exhibition spaces, Literary Park sites, plaques.
- Audiovisual documents: 15 interviews.
- Audio guides: 3 thematic itineraries

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

The main challenges faced included the difficult physical accessibility of certain locations (e.g., caves, gullies, or houses with difficult-to-navigate steps) and, in part, the "digital divide," which is more pronounced in many mountain communities than in other places. These challenges (difficult accessibility) were addressed through

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targeted technical choices (e.g., the use of drones in particularly complex survey situations). To address the digital divide, we sought to create user interfaces that were simple to use (divided into sections and categories) and as clear as possible (meaningful and well-described images). Furthermore, several meetings were held with the managers of the tourist sites to share the progress of the project and seek feedback on the graphics and content. Opportunities that could be pursued certainly include the possibility of extending the results to other contexts similar to literary parks, such as museums, archaeological sites, or cities with numerous cultural points of interest scattered throughout the area.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

The impact on stakeholders, such as the municipality of Aliano, is undoubtedly greater visibility and the ability to make various points of interest and their contents more accessible. In the specific case of Aliano, for example, the digitization of structures of high historical and cultural value, such as the Levi-Saba Museum and the Farmers' Museum, allows people to enjoy these places easily and always accessible, even when a physical visit isn't possible. Indeed, PWA mobile applications have been developed that use external QR codes to view the contents within the point of interest, which is certainly an advantage for the visibility of the assets and their accessibility.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

Several meetings were organized between Engineering, Unibo, and external companies to familiarize them with the literary parks and the most important territorial and community characteristics of Unibo, as well as the technologies already selected for the software and content development (Aton, 360° images, etc.). In several meetings, the solution design was presented, taking into account the technical developments already underway and the content already produced. Since ATON was chosen as the viewer and manager of the 360° images and 3D models, links to the ATON framework and all documentation relating to the ATON application, its use, and installation were sent to the external companies. The companies also received a tour construction manual with "ATON as it is" and some examples of potential web applications using ATON for the visualization of immersive 3D images, allowing them to begin gaining familiarity with the framework for managing immersive content. Subsequently, as the project evolved, there was a continuous exchange of information between Engineering, Unibo, and external companies to gradually clarify the developments of the various activities.

To ensure effective knowledge transfer and autonomous management of the implemented technologies, NAIS S.r.l. has developed comprehensive training materials consisting of detailed operational manuals and corresponding video tutorials:

- **Interactive Map Management Manual:** A complete guide for creating, modifying, and deleting Routes, Points of Interest (POIs), and Tour-specific POIs within the interactive mapping platform. This manual provides step-by-step instructions for content management, including geographical positioning, metadata assignment, and integration procedures for linking virtual tours to specific locations on the map.
- **Virtual Tours Management Manual:** A technical handbook detailing the procedures for creating, editing, and removing immersive virtual tours featuring 360° panoramic content using the virtual tour editor developed by NAIS S.r.l. The manual covers tour structure configuration, panoramic image integration and navigation flow optimization.
- **Video Tutorial Series:** Complementing each manual, comprehensive video guides have been produced featuring audio narration that visually demonstrate all operational procedures described in the written documentation. These multimedia resources provide users with practical, real-time examples of system navigation and content management workflows, facilitating faster learning curves and reducing potential implementation barriers.

Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

Since the conception of the VITALE project in response to the Spoke 4 call for proposals, there has been complete unity of purpose between NAIS S.r.l. and Forum Engineering S.r.l. regarding the implementation of the required activities and the division of the work to be carried out based on the specific skills of the individual companies. At the operational level, Forum Engineering S.r.l. was responsible for the creation and production of all multimedia content, while NAIS S.r.l. was responsible for the IT development of the Virtual Tours and the implementation of the materials produced. By virtue of this division of activities, during the project, the exchange of knowledge initially took place on the selection of materials to be acquired and, in the post-production phase, on the formats in which to export and release the multimedia content produced. Continuous contact through video calls and meetings allowed for constant alignment on the workflow to be adopted.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Detail the digitalisation processes

The guidelines issued by Engineering to project partners served as a reference (by Engineering) throughout many acquisition phases and were used in particular for the acquisition of 3D models and 360° images. Regarding 360° images, for the digitization of the interior and exterior environments, ENG conducted surveys using 360° photos. These surveys had the following objectives:

1. To gain an initial understanding of the environments as spaces and the level of content that could be enhanced.
2. To obtain an initial base of immersive content to use to begin building the tours.

In summary: the 360° images were taken using an Insta 360 Pro camera, mounted on a tripod and managed via an app downloaded to a tablet. For each shot, seven files were uploaded to the shared disk, corresponding to the images taken by the five cameras (JPEG), the 360° panoramic image (JPEG), and the audio track. For the 3D models, the Gaussian Splatting technique was used. This technique begins with collecting photographs of the object or scene from multiple angles, ensuring good coverage and uniform lighting. The images are then processed with photogrammetry/SfM tools, such as COLMAP or Meshroom, to obtain the camera positions and an initial 3D point cloud. This resulting cloud (e.g., as with Pontes Castle) is then pre-processed with software such as CloudCompare or Meshlab, where cleaning, noise reduction, and coordinating normalization are performed. The point cloud is then converted to Gaussian Splatting using tools such as Supersplat or gsplat, which transform the cloud into a set of Gaussian curves optimized to represent geometry and color. Finally, the resulting model is rendered on the web using compatible viewers (in Pontes' case, Splat-Viewer was used), which allowed for the production of a responsive HTML page that allows real-time interaction directly from the browser.

The process of digitalisation of multimedia content by Forum Engineering Srl professionals is described below:

The 360° images were taken using an Insta 360 Pro camera, positioned on a tripod and operated via an app downloaded onto a tablet. Seven files were then uploaded to the shared drive for each shot, corresponding to the images taken by the five cameras (Jpeg), the 360° panoramic image (Jpeg) and the audio track.

The three-dimensional reconstructions of the Pinacoteca, Casa Confino and Piazza del Belvedere were created from surveys carried out using the Leica BLK360 G2 laser scanner. Subsequently, the use of Leica Cyclone Register 360 PLUS (BLK Edition) software enabled the generation of point clouds, which were then processed and translated into meshes using the HxDR Reality Cloud Studio web app. Open-Source

Blender software was used to generate textures and repair holes in the 3D models, while the final rendering was created using Unreal Engine 5.

The three-dimensional reconstruction of the statue of Carlo Levi was generated from photogrammetric acquisitions. The bronze bust of Carlo Levi was photographed 180 times from different angles and distances, with an image overlap percentage of 75% compared to the previous shot. Thanks to Reality Capture software, the photographs were sorted and processed into a 3D model of the statue. Again, Unreal Engine 5 was used for the final rendering operations.

The high-resolution digital reproduction of the works on display at the Carlo Levi Art Gallery in Aliano and the Carlo Levi Foundation in Rome was carried out in accordance with the reference standards of the Central Institute for the Digitalisation of Cultural Heritage (ICDPC). A Sony Alpha 7R IV A camera was used with a native spatial resolution of 9504x9336 pixels in Raw format (equivalent to 62 Mp), higher than the minimum resolution of 8256x6192 pixels (equivalent to 51.4 Mp). The shooting station was also set up according to the standards, with the works, lights and camera positioned on a tripod. As indicated by the ICDPC standards, the basic settings applied were: native ISO sensitivity of the sensor and Adobe RGB 5 colour space. Before each shot, a colorimetric reference (ColorChecker) was photographed under the same lighting conditions. The digital reproduction of each painting was then uploaded to the shared project drive in both JPEG and RAW formats.

The audiovisual document consisting of 15 interviews was produced over six days of filming (Aliano from 2 to 5 March 2025 and Rome on 26 March and 8 May). The following equipment was used: Sony Alpha 7R IV A camera with Sigma 24-70/2.8 DG DN II lens; 180 cm Tripod Giant OTS professional camera tripod; Neewer RGB 960 LED SMD set light; Rode Go (Gen 3) wireless microphones and Rode VideoMic Go Rycote directional microphone; VILTROX SDI Camera Field Monitor DC-X3 camera display; - DJI Ronin-SC camera stabiliser. Once the interviews had been filmed, the professionals at Forum Engineering Srl took care of the post-production of all the material using Adobe Premiere Pro 2025 software, which was used for all editing, heading, subtitling, audio and video editing operations. At the end of the work, 15 video interviews were produced for a total of 45 minutes of edited footage. Each interview was also released in three versions in Italian, all uploaded to the shared project drive: without subtitles, with Italian subtitles.

The audio tours were produced during three recording sessions. The first took place in Aliano and was carried out by Forum Engineering operators using the Rode VideoMic Go Rycote directional microphone. The other two sessions took place in a professional studio at Fono Roma Movies & Sound under the supervision of a professional sound engineer. In both cases, the MP3 files produced were edited using

Adobe Premiere Pro 2025 software and released in 67 MP3 audio files on the shared project drive.

For Carlo Levi's Talking Pictures, the paintings and related passages from *Cristo si è fermato a Eboli* were first selected, and then a photographic acquisition campaign was carried out of the works on display in the Aliano Art Gallery. For each Talking Painting, the duration of the corresponding literary passage was set at two minutes, and Carlo Levi's voice was sampled as the narrator from interviews contained in the documentary "Carlo Levi. Altro 900" (Carlo Levi. The Other 1900). Two prototypes in MP4 format were created using Talking Avatars AI technology. This marked the start of the IT development work on the Progressive Web Application (PWA), which uses technologies and models to recognise the works of art on display and implements a three-stage visual recognition pipeline, using deep learning models optimised for mobile devices. Once the work has been recognised, the system automatically activates the audio track (MP3) of the relevant passage from *Cristo si è fermato a Eboli*, bringing Carlo Levi's painting to life thanks to his sampled voice. Given the impossibility of proceeding with the public release, two prototypes were nevertheless created and uploaded to the shared project drive.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

The design of the interactive mapping interface, developed by NAIS S.r.l., follows established UX principles specifically adapted for cultural tourism applications and diverse user demographics visiting Aliano.

User-Centered Design Principles:

- **Intuitive Navigation:** Implementation of familiar mapping interactions (zoom, pan, tap-to-select) leveraging users' existing mental models from popular map applications, reducing learning curve.
- **Progressive Information Disclosure:** Multi-layered information architecture where users can access increasingly detailed content through progressive interaction, from overview maps to specific POI details to immersive tour activation.
- **Visual Hierarchy:** Clear distinction between different content types (Routes, POIs, Tours) through consistent iconography and color coding ensuring immediate recognition of interactive elements.

Responsive and Accessible Design:

- **Cross-device Compatibility:** Adaptive interface scaling ensuring optimal usability across smartphones, tablets, and desktop devices, with touch-optimized controls and appropriate sizing for different screen densities.

Context-Aware Interface Elements:

- Seamless Tour Integration: Fluid transition from map exploration to immersive 360° experiences, maintaining spatial context and providing clear navigation pathways back to the map interface.

The resulting map interface visualized in the TOUCHSCREEN is in Figure 2.1.1.

Figure 2.1.1. Territory map interface

Regarding the design of the User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX), the following choices were made by Engineering:

- Core Layer: the customized ATON instance is the core of the platform, hosting the 3D digitization and interactive tours.
- Local Usage Layer: the touchscreen web app multilingual serves as the main onsite interface, delivering multimedia, 3D contents, maps, and tours.
- Remote Usage Layer: the three PWAs ensure continuity and portability: two dedicated to tours/pre-visits and one reproducing the touchscreen experience on the move.
- Monitoring and Governance Layer: the monitoring web app collects usage data, tracks access and allows for evaluating content dissemination across the territory.

- Technological Integration: all components share the same backend (Node.js/Express, Three.js and ATON.js for 3D/immersive content).

The ecosystem of touchscreen interface and the set of mobile PWA apps developed also follows established UX principles specifically adapted for cultural tourism applications. The touchscreen multilingual interface that integrated the complete solutions and contents produced is in Figure 2.1.2.

Figure 2.1.2. Container touchscreen

About the 3 mobile PWA multilingual developed some examples of three interfaces are shown in Figure 2.1.3.

Contents APP

Previsit APP

Tours APP

Figure 2.1.3. Three examples of the implemented interfaces for mobile.

Outline software programming design

Software design aimed to create an integrated system capable of providing information about everything the territory could offer. Beyond this, the goal was also to give users the freedom to move around and explore what the system displayed (via the mobile app). The process began with designing the content to be integrated (images, 3D models, videos, immersive photos, etc.), followed by defining possible containers (tours, galleries, maps, etc.), all seamlessly integrated into the multilingual touchscreen system.

Mobile applications were then designed with the purpose of serving as a guide along the routes to take and to assist visits in situations where access to places was difficult or even impossible.

Going into detail, Nais solution follow the following steps design of a scalable, maintainable, and high-performance Progressive Web Application architecture.

- **Interactive Map PWA**
Integration of Leaflet with OpenStreetMap for geodata rendering and real-time geolocation.
Dynamic management of routes, POIs, and tour integration points with metadata and synchronization protocols.
Interactive lateral menu for browsing routes and tours with descriptive information.
Internationalization with dynamic IT/EN content switching.
- **Immersive Virtual Tours Web Application**
Creation and configuration of panoramic 360° scenes with smooth transitions.
Interactive annotations with contextual multimedia content.
Navigation module ensuring spatial context continuity.
multi-language synchronized audio-visual content delivery.
- **Backend Infrastructure**
Node.js server extended with ATON.js, providing custom APIs for tour management, delivery optimization, and real-time synchronization.
- **Frontend Extensions**
ATON.js extensions enabling advanced visualizations, custom interactions, performance optimization, and improved user experience.

Engineering followed the following development steps:

- Installation and customization of ATON for the municipality
- Setting up an ATON instance dedicated to the municipal administration and developing the customizations needed to manage 3D content and immersive tours.
- Collection and preparation of immersive content
- Acquisition of 3D models, digitizations, and 360° photographs, forming the base content for integration into the tours.
- Post-processing of 360° images and creation of 3D tours
- Processing of panoramic photos, generation of 3D tour models, and enrichment with interactive elements.

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- Tour design and initial development
- Design of tour routes based on internal and external maps, and development of the first tours using ATON in its basic version, testing interactivity and navigation.
- Development of user and integration applications
- Creation of PWAs for local and mobile use, design of the integrated touchscreen/mobile solution, and development of the touchscreen web app that integrates all external content and functionality

Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

Regarding the multimedia content produced by NAIS and Forum Engineering, the "Quadri parlanti" (Talking Paintings) project based on Carlo Levi's works was developed on an experimental basis. Two draft versions were presented to the working group comprising Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna and Engineering SpA. However, the holder of the economic rights to Carlo Levi's intellectual property (specifically, the reproduction and distribution rights for the author's pictorial works) did not grant permission for their integration into the digital tours developed for publication, even if only for local use in Aliano. Consequently, while the Talking Paintings project was fully developed, it could not be published. Nevertheless, it should be considered a valuable opportunity for experimental research for both Forum and NAIS.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Training on use and maintenance

To ensure effective knowledge transfer and autonomous management of the implemented technologies, comprehensive training materials were produced, consisting of detailed operational manuals and corresponding video tutorials. In particular:

- Interactive Map Management Manual: a complete guide for creating, editing, and deleting routes, Points of Interest (POIs), and tour-specific POIs within the interactive mapping platform. The manual provides step-by-step instructions for content management, including geographical positioning, metadata assignment, and integration procedures to link virtual tours to specific locations on the map.
- Virtual Tour Management Manual: a technical manual describing the procedures for creating, editing, and removing immersive virtual tours with 360° panoramic content using the virtual tour editor developed by NAIS S.r.l.. The manual covers

tour structure configuration, panoramic image integration, and navigation flow optimization.

- Manual for Creating New Tours with "ATON as it is": accompanied by a package of software templates to support their construction (HTML pages ready to copy and paste, designed for displaying images, videos, models, and descriptions).
- Series of Video Tutorials: complementing each manual, complete video guides with audio narration were produced, visually demonstrating all the operational procedures described in the written documentation. These multimedia resources provide practical, real-time examples of system navigation and content management workflows, facilitating a faster learning curve and reducing potential implementation difficulties.

Describe opportunities and objectives

Opportunities certainly include the possibility of further extending the information coverage managed by the Carlo Levi Park system to an ever-increasing number of points of interest, also with a view to the opening of new exhibition sites, such as the Mask Museum. The ambitious goal could be to use the experience gained at Carlo Levi Park to improve the results obtained and extend the optimized solution to other literary parks.

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

To facilitate the understanding of the released software platforms (TOUCHSCREEN and APPS) calls with operational demos have been organised. In addition, as previously anticipated, manuals and video clips explaining the various features will be released at the end of the project.

Collect staff feedback

Much positive feedback from local governments and from bodies representing the development context (Association of Italian Literary Parks) has been collected and has helped to establish clear lines of development for the software and content.

After the inauguration phase in October, feedback (by a dedicated questionnaire) from the administration regarding what has been delivered will also be collected.

Describe the experimentation session

Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

For Aliano, the user evaluation phase has not yet started and will begin during the installation of the touchscreen. For this phase, an evaluation questionnaire was prepared based on the internal document "UX Evaluation Guidelines_wp3-wp5-ux-kpi", to be administered to at least 20–30 users.

A first comprehensive analysis of the results will be conducted subsequently, and a further evaluation and analysis will eventually be completed after the official public presentation scheduled for October 2025, when a sufficient amount of user feedback will have been collected.

Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)

Real visitors will be involved in the field testing phase to test the 360° tours (scheduled to begin late September 2025 and end late October 2025), the galleries, and the mobile PWAs. The data collected will allow the evaluation of the effectiveness, accessibility, and quality of the experience.

Considering the solution and the components of the complete system:

- Custom ATON instance for the municipality (for managing immersive 360° and 3D environments and monitoring/managing the tours)
- Interactive map (for directly identifying points of interest and viewing tours)
- 360° tours (integrated into apps for mobile exploration of points of interest)
- 3D tours (for informed exploration of points of interest via touchscreen)
- Multimedia galleries (for mobile exploration of points of interest)
- On-site interviews (for mobile exploration of points of interest)
- Progressive Web Apps for smartphones (to guide users through a real visit of the main sites)
- Documented management software (to support site managers even after the end of the project)
- Based on these components and their functional characteristics, the following SWOT analysis can be made:
 - Strengths: multilingual accessibility, immersive multimedia content, innovation with Gaussian Splatting (simple 3D surveys with good quality), easy extendibility to similar contexts.
 - Weaknesses: need for a stable connection in some areas, technical maintenance complexity.

- Opportunities: possibility to replicate the model in other literary parks using the same workflow pattern and digital containers, expansion of the target audience (youth, schools, international tourists).
- Threats: technological obsolescence and long-term update costs.

Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

During its construction phase, the project saw public engagement play a key role. Several citizens actively participated in the project, not only helping us improve the texts but also granting interviews that became digital tours. Others also provided documents and suggested locations. The digitization of some museum interiors with architectural barriers (particularly Carlo Levi's house of exile) will allow people with limited mobility to access previously inaccessible places. To make the content accessible to the blind, access points with Braille were created, and videos (and content) with subtitles were provided for the deaf. The work done for ALIANO also includes a series of activities involving local schools, with workshops and meetings with young people to conduct informational and collaborative activities in the development of works (e.g., drawings) and the production of interviews (stories told by the young people themselves), thus actively involving the young people. Other interviews were then conducted by external companies with local people who were able to share stories and legends about Calo Levi and the Alianese area. The development of the solution also addressed accessibility aspects in terms of language, and in terms of impossibility/difficulty of visiting, offering the option of a visit using personal devices (smartphones/tablets).

Conclusions

Identify technological gaps

Framework Customization Limitations: The implementation revealed significant constraints in customizing pre-packaged frameworks like ATON.js for project-specific requirements. While ATON provides robust base functionality for 3D visualization, adapting its core behaviors to meet specialized user experience demands required extensive workarounds and custom development layers, highlighting the need for more flexible, modular frameworks.

Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation

Intellectual Property Constraints: A critical unforeseen obstacle emerged regarding Carlo Levi's copyright management, preventing the deployment of the Talking Paintings application despite successful technical development. This legal barrier significantly impacted the project's innovative AI-powered artwork recognition

system, demonstrating how intellectual property considerations can override technical achievements in cultural heritage projects.

Framework Modification Challenges: Extensive modifications to ATON.js core functionalities proved more complex than anticipated, requiring deep understanding of the framework's internal architecture and custom API extensions to achieve desired user interactions and performance optimization.

Delineate further lines of research

Flexible Cultural Heritage Frameworks: Development of more adaptable, component-based frameworks specifically designed for cultural heritage applications, allowing easier customization without compromising core stability and performance.

AI Ethics and Copyright Integration: Research into technical solutions for automatically managing intellectual property constraints in AI-enhanced cultural applications, including automated copyright detection and alternative content delivery mechanisms.

Advanced Mobile AR Integration: Exploration of augmented reality technologies for mobile devices to enhance on-site visitor experiences, building upon the acquired expertise in mobile-optimized AI recognition systems.

Collaborative Content Management Systems: Development of distributed content management solutions enabling multiple stakeholders (museums, local authorities, researchers) to contribute and maintain digital cultural heritage content autonomously.

2.2. PaLeGraDeVal: The «Grazia Deledda» literary park: a valorization project using virtual technologies

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

The idea of Literary Parks originated in the late 1980s through the initiative of the Ippolito Nievo Foundation. However, its practical implementation as a strategy for local territorial development took shape thanks to the impetus provided by the European Union. Within the framework of Italy's Community Support Framework (CSF) Objective 1, programming cycle 1994/99, axis 3.1 "Incentives for Tourism Investments," the EU approved the Global Grant titled "Literary Parks". In the summer of 2009, the establishment and coordination of I Parchi Letterari® were entrusted to Paesaggio Culturale Italiano Srl, a company created to promote the Parks and related initiatives. Its aim was to position them as destinations for a specific type of tourism—cultural,

sustainable, and responsible—that could offer concrete development opportunities for local communities and businesses within a functional and efficient national network.

The Literary Park dedicated to Grazia Deledda (1871–1936) celebrates the writer from Nuoro, who won the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1926. Her works, deeply rooted in Sardinia, explore themes such as tradition, family, guilt, and the relationship with nature, making her a central figure in both Italian and international literature. In the village of Galtelli, Deledda sets one of her most important novels, *Canne al vento* (1913), as well as several short stories dedicated to local traditions.

When the project began, the Grazia Deledda Literary Park, nestled within the historic center of Galtelli, offered no technological or museum resources. It consisted only of literary plaques placed at the main spots that had inspired the novel. Without technological support, visitors were unable to explore or truly discover some locations that remain out of reach (the Castle of Pontes above all).

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

The technological development activity, led by Engineering S.p.A. and aimed at enhancing the Literary Park, focused largely on the digitization of information about the points of interest, the production of virtual tours for their exploration, and the creation of digital containers for their use. The starting point for this process was the digitization of cultural content through high-definition 2D photographs and immersive 360° images.

Initially, techniques were studied for the production of 3D models (such as NeRF), which did not require complex or costly tools, but only a standard computer and photographs. Subsequently, NeRF was replaced with and superseded by the more recent Gaussian Splatting technique which, in addition to eliminating the need for laser scanners, also does not require specialized hardware (e.g., Nvidia PC graphics cards as with NeRF).

For the visualization and manipulation of the models obtained with these techniques, the open-source ATON framework was chosen for its efficiency and flexibility in displaying 3D models, particularly in the "glTF" standard format, which also incorporated the initial 360° images. This made it possible to create interactive 3D environments for viewing multimedia content and, starting from various immersive environments, to build interactive virtual tours.

All immersive environments and content were then integrated into digital containers such as maps, galleries, and guided tour applications, accessible via touchscreen displays or mobile devices. Everything developed is made available through integrated touchscreen applications and smartphone apps.

The external company, Risviel srl, adopted an integrated system based on:

- WordPress as a CMS for multilingual management and publication of content, both on the website (parcodeledda.it) and on the interactive totem. This approach allows for a single management point with two layout modes: one optimized for the totem's touchscreen and another for classic web browsing.
- Custom-developed WordPress plugin, designed to graphically add interactive areas and markers to 360° photos.
- Three.js, a WebGL library chosen as a flexible and efficient solution.
- PostgreSQL/PostGIS as the database to store the data managed by the plugin (points of interest, interactive areas, markers), making them also usable in GIS contexts. The plugin configuration is saved in the WordPress database.
- Multimedia totem based on a custom Linux system, optimized for stability and usability.
- Digitization techniques: 3D scans, drone acquisitions, 360° images, photogrammetric surveys.

Engineering has developed an architecture in which the ATON Framework represents the technological core, while content distribution takes place through applications dedicated to different scenarios (touchscreen, mobility, monitoring).

1. Core Layer – Immersive and 3D Content Management

- Key Component: Customized ATON instance.
- Technologies: Node.js, Express, MongoDB, ATON.js framework (custom API extensions), and Three.js for 3D/360 rendering.
- Function: 3D model repository and delivery engine (glTF/GLB, OBJ, PLY), enriched digitizations with multimedia hotspots and interactive tours.

2. Local Usage Layer – Touchscreen Interface

- Key component: Web application for kiosks and interactive screens.
- Technologies: HTML5, CSS3, JavaScript, CSS, Leaflet/OpenStreetMap map library.
- Function: Main onsite access point, with a responsive interface optimized for touch, timeout management, and multimedia content container. This application integrates all the content and containers developed, including the GIS map described above and produced by the external company.

3. Remote Access Layer – Mobile PWAs

- Components:
 - PWA 1 → 360° mobile tour.
 - PWA 2 → Pre-visit of locations.
 - Technologies: JavaScript, service workers, Web App Manifest for mobile installation.
 - Function: Continuity of access outside the physical context, with experiences optimized for smartphones and tablets, maintaining content and interface consistency with touchscreens.
4. Monitoring and Governance Layer – Content Supervision
- Key component: Monitoring and analysis web app.
 - Technologies: HTML5, CSS3, JavaScript, Node.js backend, Leaflet map libraries.
 - Function: Usage data collection, monitoring of POIs and content across the territory, with visualization tools for all released applications, and online user manuals.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

Among the main challenges that had to be addressed, one must certainly consider the difficult physical accessibility of certain sites such as the Pontes Castle or Mount Tuttavista and, to some extent, the “digital divide,” which is often more pronounced in small towns than in other areas. Accessibility issues were tackled through targeted technical choices, such as the use of drones in particularly complex survey situations. To address the digital divide, efforts were made to design user interfaces that were simple and intuitive to use, with solutions such as dividing content into sections and categories or incorporating visually engaging and well-described images. To ensure timely feedback, several meetings were organized during the course of the Project with the site managers, allowing for the sharing of progress and the collection of input regarding design choices and content.

Another challenge was to successfully bring together the different research teams involved, along with their sub-projects, into a fruitful collaboration. Among these, one may note the studies on the archaeological sites surrounding Galtelli, carried out by archaeologists from the Department of History and Cultures (DISCI) at the University of Bologna, and the educational and community workshops promoted by the team at the University of Bari.

From a research perspective, the greatest opportunity will be to extend the results achieved to other similar contexts, such as additional Literary Parks, other open-air

museums, archaeological sites, or larger territories rich in numerous cultural points of interest.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

The effects on stakeholders, as in our case with the Municipality of Galtellì benefiting from the Project, involve many aspects, such as gaining greater visibility within the tourism offer, as well as the chance to make the various points of interest and their content more accessible or to position itself as the leader of an innovative and multi-layered initiative.

In the specific case of Galtellì, for example, the digitization of sites with high historical and cultural value but difficult to access, such as Pontes Castle, allows visitors to view and explore them remotely without difficulty. Similarly, applications that enable the visualization of content inside a point of interest via external QR codes provide an additional advantage for both the visibility and accessibility of these assets.

The project also has positive effects on local tour and environmental guides, because, without replacing them, it offers visitors an overview of what the town has to offer through small previews that encourage further exploration.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

The sharing of knowledge regarding project requirements and the available technologies has been carried out over the years jointly by Engineering and Unibo, through online meetings to align the companies on what had been developed and what was yet to be developed, on the results achieved at each stage, and on the objectives to be pursued. From a technical standpoint, the companies were provided with links and official documentation on the ATON tool in order to review and study it with a view to using it for the construction and visualization of immersive environments. In addition, a user manual for ATON "as it is" was provided for the creation of immersive tours. Finally, during the development phases, frequent alignment sessions were held to achieve the final integration of the solution.

Moreover, guidelines and clarifications were provided to the external company to ensure the correct development of the proposed solutions, such as the graphic and functional features of the interactive and configurable territorial map, which enables the use of immersive environments, or the characteristics of the web app dedicated to the game, based on the literary plaques of Grazia Deledda scattered throughout the town.

Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

The winning company, Risviel srl, shared:

- Technical expertise in WordPress configuration and the development of custom plugins integrated with external databases;
- Specific knowledge in the use of Three.js for managing 3D models, immersive images, and interactive content, as an alternative to ATON;
- Methodologies for digitizing cultural assets (photogrammetry, 360° captures, drones, laser scanning);
- Experience in multimedia documentation and strategies for delivery via totems and the web;
- Best practices to ensure content accessibility, multilingual support, and usability.
- Methodologies and practical skills on how video interviews were produced, through collaboration with the subcontractor Mammut Film Srl.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Detail the digitalisation processes

Regarding the digitization of internal and external environments, Engineering conducted surveys using 360° photos with the following purposes:

- To gain an initial understanding of the spaces in terms of layout and the level of content that could potentially be enhanced;
- To obtain a preliminary set of immersive content to begin the construction of the tours.

The acquisition process and best practices to follow are described as follows. As for the 3D models, the Gaussian Splatting technique was applied during the creation process. This begins with collecting photographs of the object or scene from multiple angles, ensuring good coverage and uniform lighting. The images are then processed using photogrammetry/Structure-from-Motion (SfM) tools, such as COLMAP or Meshroom, to obtain camera positions and an initial 3D point cloud. This point cloud (e.g., for Pontes Castle) is subsequently pre-processed using software such as CloudCompare or MeshLab, where cleaning, noise reduction, and coordinate normalization are performed. At this stage, the point cloud is converted to Gaussian Splatting using tools like Supersplat or gsplat, which transform the cloud into a set of

optimized Gaussians to represent geometry and color. Finally, the resulting model is rendered on the web via compatible viewers (Splat-Viewer was used for Pontes Castle), producing a responsive HTML page that allows real-time interaction directly from a browser.

The external company Risviel Srl carried out the following digitization processes:

- Aerial acquisitions with drones, to obtain panoramic shots and territorial models.
- 360° photographic and video captures, for the creation of immersive environments accessible via totems and the web.
- A 3D model derived from photogrammetry and laser scanning, subsequently optimized to ensure compatibility with playback devices (casa delle dame Pintor).
- Integration of all digital content into WordPress and the PostgreSQL database, with the possibility of linking to GIS maps.
- Reconstruction of the Pintor "Casa delle Dame", made accessible through 360° virtual photos to overcome the heaviness of the full 3D model and ensure smoother navigation.

The digitization project of the "Casa delle Dame" involved the 3D digital reconstruction of Casa Nieddu, described in Grazia Deledda's novel *Canne al vento* as the house of the Dame Pintor. The reconstruction was primarily based on the analysis of images from *Canne al vento - Lo sceneggiato*, a miniseries produced in 1958. In the first phase, significant frames from the footage were extracted and reworked to serve as documentary references for the preliminary graphic elaboration. Subsequently, using Autodesk Revit, the architectural structure of the building was modeled, with particular attention to structural and spatial elements. The following phase, carried out with Blender, allowed the integration of material details and the definition of textures, as well as the inclusion of furniture and objects typical of early 20th-century Sardinian culture, to provide a coherent historical and environmental context.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

Regarding the design of the User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX), the following choices were made by Risviel:

- Frontend: web interface with an interactive map, informational panels, 360° photos, 3D models, and multimedia content.
- Backend: WordPress administration panel enhanced with the custom plugin, allowing operators to easily add and manage markers and interactive areas.
- Interactive totem: simplified touchscreen interface, optimized for public use, with intuitive navigation and quick access to content.

- UX design: focus on accessibility, multilingual support, and performance, ensuring fast loading times and smooth navigation.

Figure 2.2.1. The user interface developed.

Regarding the design of the User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX), the following choices were made by Engineering:

- Core Layer: the customized ATON instance is the core of the platform, hosting the 3D digitization and interactive tours.
- Local Usage Layer: the touchscreen web app serves as the main onsite interface, delivering multimedia, 3D contents, maps, and tours.
- Remote Usage Layer: the three PWAs ensure continuity and portability: two dedicated to tours/pre-visits and one reproducing the touchscreen experience on the move.
- Monitoring and Governance Layer: the monitoring web app collects usage data, tracks access and allows for evaluating content dissemination across the territory.
- Technological Integration: all components share the same backend (Node.js/Express, Three.js and ATON.js for 3D/immersive content).

The touchscreen interface that integrated the complete solution is shown in Figure 2.2.2.

Figure 2.2.2. Interface of the touchscreen.

As for the multilingual pre-visit PWA app, the interface is shown in Figure 2.2.3.

Figure 2.2.3. Interface of the pre-visit PWA app.

Outline software programming design

Regarding software design and development, Risviel implemented the following:

- Development of a custom WordPress plugin based on Three.js, to create and manage interactive areas and points of interest on 360° photos.
- Integration of the plugin-managed data into PostgreSQL/PostGIS, ensuring data persistence and usability within a GIS context.
- Configuration and synchronization of WordPress content in two formats: touchscreen layout for the totem, classic layout for the website.
- Modular architecture, designed to support future extensions (e.g., additional GIS layers, links to 3D models, analytics dashboards).

Engineering followed the following development steps:

- Installation and customization of ATON for the municipality
- Setting up an ATON instance dedicated to the municipal administration and developing the customizations needed to manage 3D content and immersive tours.
- Collection and preparation of immersive content
- Acquisition of 3D models, digitizations, and 360° photographs, forming the base content for integration into the tours.
- Post-processing of 360° images and creation of 3D tours
- Processing of panoramic photos, generation of 3D tour models, and enrichment with interactive elements.

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- Tour design and initial development
- Design of tour routes based on internal and external maps, and development of the first tours using ATON in its basic version, testing interactivity and navigation.
- Development of user and integration applications
- Creation of PWAs for local and mobile use, design of the integrated touchscreen/mobile solution, and development of the touchscreen web app that integrates all external content and functionality.

Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

ATON was not adopted by Risviel due to limited documentation and insufficient support. The choice fell on Three.js, which provided greater control and reliability.

Ultra-high-resolution 3D models were not used: the files were too heavy for the totem and web usage. Optimized models were preferred, ensuring accessibility and smooth performance.

Complex immersive virtual reality systems with headsets were not implemented, due to budget constraints and to ensure more inclusive access via web and totem.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Training on use and maintenance

Stakeholders, such as guides and local administrations, received explanations and updates throughout all phases of the project implementation. They also will receive further information, through manuals, videos, and tools for the use and maintenance of the developed products. In addition, during the installation phase, a practical demonstration of the TOUCHSCREEN and the APPS will be provided.

Describe opportunities and objectives

The goal for the stakeholders was to make them independent in using the touchscreens, the PWAs, and the management web app. Therefore, in addition to providing hands-on demonstrations of how the applications work, several documents were created (e.g., manuals and videos).

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

As mentioned earlier, a documentation package for the applications will be released, consisting of manuals and short video clips demonstrating how to use the applications.

Collect staff feedback

After the initial inauguration phase held in September, feedback from users and the local administration regarding the details of the developed products will be collected through questionnaires following the guidelines prepared by WP5.

Describe the experimentation session

Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

For Galtelli, the user evaluation phase began during the installation of the touchscreen. In this phase, a questionnaire based on the internal document "UX Evaluation Guidelines_wp3-wp5-ux-kpi" was created and administered to users, yielding positive evaluation results. A complete analysis of the results will be carried out over time, between the dissemination activities scheduled for October 2025 and the official inauguration planned for spring 2026, when enough user feedback will be available.

So far, real visitors have been involved in testing the 360° tours, galleries, and PWAs. The data collected have already partially allowed for a positive assessment of the effectiveness, accessibility, and overall quality of the experience.

Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)

Strengths: multilingual accessibility, immersive multimedia content, innovation with Gaussian Splatting.

Weaknesses: need for a stable connection in some areas, technical maintenance complexity.

Opportunities: possibility to replicate the model in other Literary Parks, expansion of the target audience (youth, schools, international tourists).

Threats: technological obsolescence, long-term update costs.

Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

The system has promoted active participation, social inclusion, and accessibility, also thanks to its availability in multiple languages and use on personal devices.

Conclusions

Identify technological gaps

Technological gaps: lack of stable network infrastructure in the area, need for simpler maintenance tools for non-technical operators.

Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation

Unexpected issues: longer production times for 360° content, adaptation of 3D models to the performance of mobile devices.

Delineate further lines of research

Future research and development directions: integration of augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and artificial intelligence systems for route personalization and automatic recognition of cultural content.

3. Research case studies

3.1. ThERA – Theran Epigraphic Rubbings Archive

Outline clear goals and objectives

The ThERA (Theran Epigraphic Rubbings Archive) project aims to create a sustainable and interoperable digital archive for the collection of rubbings from the Agora of the Gods at Thera.

Its objectives are:

- Digitize and link high-resolution rubbings to their inscriptions via a custom deep-zoom viewer.
- Digitally encode the entire corpus using the TEI-EpiDoc standard to ensure FAIR-compliant data.
- Georeference the inscriptions and integrate them into a QGIS-based spatial layer for an interactive map.
- Build a bilingual (Italian/English) website to provide open access to the corpus and foster public engagement.
- Contribute to best practices for digital archives of archaeological and epigraphic heritage.

Initial situation

Before ThERA, the inscriptions lacked a unified digital edition and standardized metadata. Rubbings existed only as fragile paper copies stored in the Greek Epigraphy Laboratory at Tor Vergata, with no online accessibility. There was no georeferenced dataset or interactive map.

Chosen technologies:

- TEI-EpiDoc XML encoding for structured, machine-readable editions.
- QGIS for georeferencing and interactive spatial visualization.
- OpenSeadragon for deep-zoom visualization of high-resolution rubbings.
- Custom back-end/front-end for XML management and user interaction.
- Cloudflare hosting and a custom domain for long-term accessibility.

Challenges:

- Converting paper rubbings to digital format while maintaining archival quality.
- Managing very large image files in the Cloudflare hosting environment.
- Ensuring interoperability and metadata consistency.
- Designing a web interface suitable for both scholarly and general audiences.

Opportunities:

- Creating a replicable model for digital dissemination of site-specific archives.
- Enhancing public engagement by combining textual, visual, and spatial data.
- Supporting Spoke 4 objectives on FAIR data and innovative cultural heritage narratives.

Potential effects on the involved stakeholders:

- Museums and archaeologists: Gain access to interoperable digital editions and spatially linked data for research and exhibitions.
- Local public bodies: Benefit from a platform that enhances the cultural visibility of Thera and can support heritage promotion and education.
- Scholars and students: Access a user-friendly digital corpus that can be reused for research and teaching.
- General public and tourists: Explore rubbings and inscriptions interactively, increasing understanding and appreciation of cultural heritage.- General public

and tourists: Explore rubbings and inscriptions interactively, increasing understanding and appreciation of cultural heritage.

Knowledge sharing among project participants

Knowledge exchange occurred through:

- Regular team meetings to align scholarly and technical work.
- Close collaboration between the epigraphist and the developer to refine XML encoding, map integration, and image linking and create the website.
- Joint publication ("A heritage of paper and stone: the ThERA project", Science and Technology for Cultural Heritage, 2024) presenting methodologies and outcomes.

Planned Training Activities and Knowledge Exchange:

- Internal workshops on TEI-EpiDoc encoding, QGIS georeferencing, and OpenSeadragon use.
- Documentation to ensure sustainable management of the platform.
- The back-end interface was designed for non-technical users, enabling long-term content updates by future curators.

Use of guidelines and prototypes identified (WP3)

- ThERA follows international TEI-EpiDoc guidelines, ensuring interoperability and FAIR compliance.
- Metadata is structured to allow future integration with linked open data platforms.
- WP3 prototypes were not reused, as a fully custom infrastructure was developed specifically for epigraphic material.

Digitisation:

- High-resolution photographs of rubbings using multiple parallel axis gigapixel photography and XML encoding of inscriptions

UI/UX:

- A bilingual website with filters, a browsable interface, and an interactive map.

Software Design:

- A back-end for XML/HTML management and a front-end integrating OpenSeadragon and QGIS layers.

What Has Not Been Used and Why:

- External WP3 prototypes were not applied, because ThERA needed specialized tools for epigraphic encoding (TEI-EpiDoc XML) and integration with QGIS and OpenSeadragon – solutions that are highly specific to inscriptions and rubbings. Therefore, instead of taking a generic prototype from WP3 and adapting it, the team developed a bespoke technical infrastructure – a tailor-made back-end and front-end, plus the map and viewer – that directly fits the needs of the rubbing and epigraphic archive.

Planned Introduction of Technology to Stakeholders

- Training and documentation allow curators and scholars to manage the archive
- Planned workshops will introduce the platform to local heritage professionals.
- Internal testing sessions provided feedback for interface refinements
- Staff feedback: Internal team testing confirmed that the platform is intuitive and functional.

Feedback highlighted the need for improved large-image loading performance, which is being addressed with Cloudflare configuration.

Evaluation and Experimentation

SWOT Summary

Strengths:

- Integration of textual, visual, and spatial data; adherence to standards; bilingual interface

Weaknesses:

- Limited spatial precision for some inscriptions. Some inscriptions could not be mapped with high spatial precision due to the lack of detailed on-site georeferencing. Future fieldwork at the Agora of the Gods will be necessary to collect precise GPS data for each inscription.

Opportunities:

- Replicable model for other archives; increased public engagement.

Threats:

- Long-term hosting and maintenance require sustained institutional support
- The solutions developed promote accessibility, citizen participation, and inclusion by freely sharing inscriptions and rubbings online.

Conclusions and Further Research

Technological Gaps:

- Automated palaeographic tagging and advanced linked open data integration remain to be developed;

Unforeseen Issues:

- The publication of very large images on Cloudflare required additional technical work.

Next Steps:

- Beta testing of the website is scheduled for September 2025, with final refinements before the full public release.
- Future research will enhance palaeographic tagging and enable broader interoperability with other similar projects.

3.2. The Hidden Legacy. Byzantine Seals of the Exarchal Age in Italian Museum Collections

Outline clear goals and objectives

The project "The Hidden Legacy. Byzantine Seals of the Exarchal Age in Italian Museum Collections" focuses on the collection, study and digitalization of Byzantine seals from the Exarchal period (584–751 AD) discovered in Italy or preserved in Italian museum collections. The project, therefore, fits into the context of national and international museums that preserve this type of Byzantine cultural evidence.

Byzantine sigillography is an interdisciplinary field of study that examines seals once affixed to official documents within the Eastern Roman Empire and its provinces, including Italy during the so-called Exarchal period (584–751 AD). The exarchate was a territorial and administrative unit of the Byzantine province in Italy under the command of the exarch, an imperial official whose authority derived from Constantinople.

Byzantine society made extensive use of seals in daily administration as well as private correspondence. Byzantine seals are coin-like objects, mostly made of lead, with inscriptions and/or iconography on both sides. Their legends usually reveal the owner's name, titles, and functions—whether administrative, religious, civil, or military. They therefore offer valuable insights into Late Antique and Medieval Mediterranean history, from language (Greek and Latin), palaeography, and onomastics to administrative and religious history. It is evident that they also serve as a significant source of our knowledge regarding the bureaucratic and social system of Byzantine Italy between Late Antiquity and the early Middle Ages.

Until now, this material evidence of Byzantine administration has been scattered across printed editions and specialized publications, complicating systematic access and analysis.

Furthermore, the absence of widely shared standards for their publication further complicates their searchability and study. The only significant digital edition of Byzantine seals is the online catalogue of the Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection in Washington DC, which contains around 17,000 specimens. However, there has been no centralised digital infrastructure for Byzantine seals, nor for the seals of the Exarchal period in Italy.

To address this gap, the project has adopted SigiDoc, an XML-based and TEI-compliant standard for encoding and publishing sigillographic documents. Developed by researchers in Paris and Cologne, SigiDoc provides standardized guidelines and tools for creating reliable digital editions of sigillographic materials. The system is integrated into the EFES platform (EpiDoc Front-End Service), which has been customized for the visualization and consultation of seals. The implementation of SigiDoc represents a challenge due to the need to ensure data consistency and scientific accuracy, but it also provides opportunities to standardize editions, improve searchability and interoperability, and foster collaborative research. A centralized search interface is also planned in the near future, enabling the virtual unification of all corpora encoded in SigiDoc, including this project's dataset of Exarchal seals preserved in Italian museums. This will make all its data accessible and interoperable, thereby providing a valuable resource for the historical study of the functioning of the Byzantine administrative machine and its historical actors in the context of the Italian peninsula in the early Middle Ages.

The project strategy involves the following stages:

- Collecting and organizing Byzantine seals of the Exarchal period preserved in Italian museum collections and published in printed catalogues (such as the seals of the Vatican Library) or dispersed in journals and miscellaneous volumes (including the unpublished seals of the National Museum of Ravenna identified by the project researcher).

- Collecting and organizing Exarchal seals discovered in archaeological excavations in Italy or acquired in Italy and now preserved in foreign collections.
- Analyzing and studying the collected material for possible re-attributions and re-dating.
- Digitizing all collected Exarchal seals according to the SigiDoc standard.

The use of SigiDoc also benefits museums and public stakeholders by centralizing and making accessible a cultural heritage that is otherwise difficult for non-specialist audiences to access and understand, thereby enhancing both its scientific and cultural value.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Knowledge transfer was achieved through the training of the researcher involved in the project. This training was provided by Digital Byzantine Studies (DiBS) team at the University of Cologne in a dedicated workshop. The workshop equipped the researcher with the skills needed to encode seals digitally, use the EFES platform effectively, and produce diplomatic and interpretative editions in line with SigiDoc standards. This ensured consistent application of best practices throughout the project, in line with the established SigiDoc methodology.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

The digitalization process, still ongoing, follows the SigiDoc guidelines. Each seal is encoded with detailed metadata covering its physical characteristics, provenance, dating, inscriptions, iconography, and bibliographic references. The EFES platform has been customized to provide a clear and navigable interface, allowing users to view seal images alongside diplomatic and interpretative editions as well as the underlying XML markup.

Special attention is given to the paleographic rendering of inscriptions, with the Athena Ruby font ensuring accuracy and readability. This makes the digital editions scientifically robust while also keeping them accessible for comparative analyses and collaborative research across collections in the future.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Following the conclusion of the digitization phase and its integration with the centralised search interface on the SigiDoc platform, the project will shift its focus to the dissemination of results and the exploration of their potential for implementation and reuse. This will foster scholarly discussion, review and correction, thus promoting best practices in collaborative research. In the near future, a tagless editor developed by the creators of SigiDoc will be available. This tool will make the SigiDoc template accessible to those with no specific training in XML and the SigiDoc standard, including museum staff. Another future objective of the project could be to introduce this new tool to interested Italian museum staff.

Describe the experimentation session

User-based testing has not yet been completed, as the digitalization process is still in progress. Nevertheless, the pilot edition of a small group of Byzantine seals has already demonstrated that SigiDoc significantly enhances data discoverability and facilitates paleographic analysis. Preliminary evaluation highlights the strengths of the approach, including interoperability of data, standardized metadata, and support for collaborative research.

Conclusions

The implementation phase has revealed technological gaps, such as the need for further integration with Linked Open Data repositories and the development of more intuitive interfaces for non-specialists. Other challenges include the technical complexity of XML encoding and the need to standardize digitalizations across different collections.

Future directions include the completion of the ongoing digitalization, the possible expansion to other medieval seal collections preserved in Italy, the integration of the project's dataset into the centralized SigiDoc interface, and alignment with European infrastructures and FAIR principles to ensure long-term sustainability and integration of the data into the broader digital cultural heritage ecosystem.

In this way, the project contributes to SigiDoc's broader objective of promoting open access, public engagement, accessibility, and inclusion in the study of Byzantine sigillographic heritage.

3.3. Digital strategies for enhancing cultural heritage: the Villa del Casale of Piazza Armerina, from the late antique building site to the Museum Collection

Outline clear goals and objectives

Identify and describe the peculiarities of the museum type

The project "Digital strategies for enhancing cultural heritage: the Villa del Casale of Piazza Armerina, from the late antique building site to the Museum Collection" focuses on the Trigona Palace Museum of Piazza Armerina, EN (Type D Museum), in its interlinked relationship with the archaeological context of Villa del Casale of Piazza Armerina.

Erected at the end of the 17th century and completed in the first half of the 18th century, the Trigona Palace stands as one of the most authoritative examples of late Sicilian Baroque civil architecture. In 1959, the palace was acquired by the Regional Administration for Sicilian Cultural Heritage to house the Museum of the City and Territory of Piazza Armerina. It is organized around four levels: the ground floor entails a multimedia conference room and laboratories; the mezzanine floor is partly used for offices and partly for an exhibition about the archaeology of the territory, including findings from the Villa del Casale; the first floor, the so-called 'piano nobile' (main floor), showcases the local cultural heritage from the Middle Ages to the 20th century. A small section of the museum is devoted to the exhibit of the Villa del Casale di Piazza Armerina heritage, an exceptional archaeological site not only for the Sicilian but also for the global Mediterranean cultural heritage.

Due to its exceptional wealth of architectural and decorative elements with more than 3000 sq of mosaics, the Villa del Casale has been included in the UNESCO World Heritage List since 1997. The management of the Villa is entrusted to the Archaeological Park of Morgantina and the Roman Villa del Casale in Piazza Armerina. Generally appreciated for the imposing decoration of the 4th c. residence, for centuries it played the role of key landscape marker with an almost uninterrupted occupation from the so-called Villa Rustica (end of the 1st c. AD) to the Medieval village (12th c. AD). This settlement palimpsest has been brought to light during many excavation seasons lasting from the second half of the 19th century to 2014. After a short break, since 2022 scientific activities have been resumed under the coordination of the University of Bologna and the auspices of CISEM (Centro Interuniversitario di Studi sull'Edilizia nel Mediterraneo tardoantico). The University of South Florida cooperates to the project with reference to the digital curation and technical implementation.

Describe the initial situation

The Palazzo Trigona Museum collection aims to showcase the historical development of the Villa del Casale through select excavation findings. Nevertheless, only a fraction of its extensive heritage is currently on display. In addition, distance between the Museum and the Villa (about 6.5 km) frequently hinders the development of a cohesive itinerary linking the two sites.

Moreover, there is a substantial mismatch in the quality of the information conveyed in the visit itineraries. The didactic apparatus produced for the Museum, with a diachronic path through the monument's main settlement phases, cannot be enjoyed in situ, that is, when the visitor is actually inside the Villa. There, the didactic apparatus is very deficient and outdated. The same is true for the multimedia equipment entailed in the Museum exhibition, that are a couple of interactive touch-screen tables that allow a historical reading of the different periods, that are completely lacking in the Villa in-situ visitors' itinerary. Moreover, most of the relevant findings are currently inaccessible to the public, since they are stored in the Villa warehouses.

To bridge these gaps, the creation of a web-based digital ecosystem intends to expand users' perception of Piazza Armerina cultural heritage and provides them with a novel, updated and comprehensive understanding of its historical developments. By enhancing Museum exhibits and virtually accessing artifacts stored in the Villa's storerooms, the project seeks to enrich visitors' experiences and promote cultural exchange.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

This research case study, part of the broader archaeological project launched in 2022, combines the digitization of archival and legacy data with an extensive 3D documentation campaign focused on structures and artifacts. The latter involves the use of advanced technologies, including 3D surveying, geospatial analysis, terrestrial laser scanning, digital photogrammetry, and structured light 3D scanning.

The project strategy involves the following stages:

- Collection, organization, and digitization of existing data within a GIS platform to assess the consistency and spatial distribution of various categories of findings from Villa del Casale excavations across different settlement phases.
- Recovery, catalogue, and digitization of a large group of artifacts from Gentili's excavations, previously scattered in the Villa's storerooms and partly exposed at Palazzo Trigona.
- Completion of the 3D scanning of the entirety of the exterior of the Villa complex, combined with data from a prior digitization campaign that focused on the Villa's mosaics, ending in the creation of a 3D scan of the entirety of the Villa complex.

- Publication of the historical and technical metadata of the materials through a Content Management System, aimed at improving access to previously unavailable resources and supporting both scientific research and the virtual recontextualization of the finds from Gentili's excavations. A digital platform was created via Omeka Classic to host and display 2D and 3D replicas of artifacts and archival materials. Further experimentations will regard the upload of the Villa model on ATON, along with the virtual replacement of some of the 3D scanned artefacts.
- A thorough review of primary archival collections held by regional Superintendencies. This activity led to the discovery of partially unpublished graphic and photographic documents, including images of key excavation phases and the monument's condition before extensive 20th-century restorations. Administrative and epistolary documents also shed light on the logistical and operational challenges of early archaeological activities, providing valuable insights into significant discoveries. Among them, an unauthored and undated excavation diary was recovered, that has been transcribed and analyzed through AI techniques (Transkribus; HTR; HAT). These materials have been digitally processed, showcased in digital collections, and will be further enhanced in virtual exhibitions.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

The project aims at expanding the users' current perception of Piazza Armerina cultural heritage with the creation of a web-based digital environment for enhancing both findings on display in the Museum and a wide-range of artefacts stored in the Villa del Casale storerooms. Using cutting-edge digital technologies, the project envisages producing a variety of digital resources to retrace and enrich the thread of memory both in relation to the monument history and the multifaceted circumstances that led to its discovery. Providing free access to a wide range of digital resources, the project pursues the final goal of improving users' involvement both remotely and in situ. By generating immersive visualizations and accurate reconstructions, it aims at creating enriched visitor experiences and new thematic tourist routes, allowing broader and more engaging access to the monument's history.

One of the project's major goals is the development of an open-access, web-based digital platform to host, present, and freely share all the materials produced during the project's lifespan. The virtual environment will feature several key sections, including:

- a digital archive of historic photographs and excavation diaries from the earliest excavation seasons.
- virtual reconstruction of the Villa, along with galleries of 3D artifact models accompanied by curated metadata;

- thematic virtual exhibitions exploring topics such as the key figures involved in the Villa's discovery, the construction history of the site, its architectural features, and its decorative program.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

The digital heritage strategy surrounding the Villa del Casale seeks to generate significant impact across multiple stakeholder groups—including museums, educational institutions, local authorities, and the broader public. By digitizing fragile or inaccessible artefacts through advanced 2D and 3D scanning, the project enhances conservation efforts while expanding access to cultural resources. Museums and local public bodies benefit from high-fidelity digital models that support both scholarly research and public engagement. Furthermore, immersive virtual experiences and multimedia tools facilitate educational outreach and cultural tourism, fostering broader community involvement. This approach not only preserves and disseminates cultural heritage but also repositions the Villa del Casale as an accessible, dynamic site of historical interpretation and collective memory.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

The digitization in 3D of about 100 artefacts among archaeological findings stored in the Villa's storerooms and on show at Palazzo Trigona Museum was carried out using handheld digital photogrammetry techniques and an Artec Space Spider structured light scanner.

The completion of the 3D scanning of the entirety of the exterior of the Villa complex was performed using Faro Focus premium Terrestrial Laser Scanners, combined with data from a prior digitization campaign that focused on the Villa's mosaics, ending in the creation of a 3D scan of the entirety of the villa complex with an accuracy of $\pm 1\text{mm}$ at 10m.

Part of the collection (a selection of digital twins of objects from the baths complex of the Villa del Casale) has been already post-processed and progressively uploaded on <https://www.cisemda.com/>, encompassing metadata for both traditional and digital CH objects. Currently, 3D models are available on a sketchfab collection but future steps in content upload and visualization will entail the models upload on the open-source Web3D framework ATON, with the selection of specific Points of Interest (Pols). Semantic metadata enrichment will be ensured by the adoption of ontologies and existing standards, such as CIDOC CRM, integrating application profiles for

specific targets, such as CHAD-AP for the description of acquisition and digitization workflow.

As far as the digital storytelling strategies outlined by WP3, the project will adopt a space-centric enhancement approach and a real-time narrative line mostly focused on historical annotation in order to enhance the great array of legacy data recovered to be overlapped with physical space and interlinked with digital surrogated of objects and spaces.

Informative storytelling techniques will be exploited to integrate historical data, cultural features with digital annotations and 3D visualizations.

As far as digital augmentation, data visualization will be used to overlay detailed information about the objects on display, making connections between artifacts, discoveries, biographies of archaeological research key figures and ancient owners of the Villa, historical event and contexts.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

The collaboration between the participating research institutes and the on-site activities is governed by a formal agreement with the Director of the Archaeological Park of Morgantina and Villa del Casale in Piazza Armerina. In accordance with the research objectives outlined in this agreement, the next digitization campaign is scheduled for June 2025. Following the completion of the digitization phase and the development of a digital environment enriched with curated metadata, the project will shift its focus toward capacity-building initiatives, including training sessions and knowledge exchange with museum personnel and local stakeholders.

Describe the experimentation session

All the experimental sessions will be held in the near future.

Conclusions

The final release of the Piazza Armerina web platform is planned for the near future. It will be fully accessible to the public across all its sections. QR codes placed at key locations within both the Palazzo Trigona Museum and the Villa del Casale will facilitate access to the platform, encouraging integrated visitor itineraries between the two sites and enhancing the overall experience through curated and immersive digital content.

3.4. Museo Storico Italiano della Guerra (Rovereto)

Outline clear goals and objectives

Identify and describe the peculiarities of the museum type

MITAG is hosted in Rovereto Castle, a site of strong symbolic and historical value. Its collections span from the 19th century to the Second World War, including uniforms, weapons, photographs, and documents. As such, it is categorized as a Type D museum.

Describe the initial situation

In recent years, MITAG has undergone a cultural and communicative renewal. The museum launched a new institutional identity, inaugurated a decolonial exhibition on Italian colonialism in 2025, and organized a cycle of public meetings. At the same time, it activated a digital archive and produced a podcast, both designed to extend access and reach remote audiences.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

The museum introduced several tools: the Archiui digital archive; the podcast 'Cose di fronte'; online educational and video materials; the 2025 decolonial exhibition; a catalogue of the collection of material testimonies related to the Italian colonial experience held in Trentino and South Tyrolean museums. These solutions are intended to enhance accessibility, democratize knowledge, and provide inclusive narratives. My work consists of analysing and evaluating these solutions and potential future improvements and developments, with respect to the goals of accessibility and enhancement of the museum's heritage.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

Challenges: making the digital archive more thematic and user-friendly; improving digital tools with onsite experiences; ensuring inclusion of community perspectives. Opportunities: consolidating the renewal process; using exhibitions and podcasts as laboratories for new narratives; and expanding participation through digital means.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

Stakeholders include the museum itself, the Autonomous Province of Trento, local and school communities, scholars, visitors, remote audiences, and other regional museums. Effects may include stronger collaboration, increased visibility, and implementation of best practices of inclusive heritage management.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

Training activities could include workshops to strengthen staff digital competences (managing online archives, podcasts, accessible content) combined with seminars on decolonial approaches. These sessions would ensure staff are able to use digital tools effectively while framing them within inclusive and critical narratives.

Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

Knowledge exchange can be strengthened through collaborations with universities, non-academic institutions and associations, focusing on the critical and inclusive use of digital archives and storytelling tools.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Detail the digitalisation processes

MITAG's digital archive provides access to collections but is currently organized mainly as an inventory, limiting thematic exploration.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

The current design is functional for experts but less intuitive for general audiences. Developing thematic paths, timelines, and maps could improve UX.

Outline software programming design

Not directly developed by the museum; instead, external platforms such as Archiui are used.

Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

Advanced personalization or participatory digital tools have not yet been implemented, mainly due to resource limitations and the focus on initial accessibility.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Training on use and maintenance

Staff are introduced to new tools through discussions and collaborations, with potential for more structured workshops.

Describe opportunities and objectives

The objective is to improve the implementation of digital tools to foster strategies of valorisation of the museum and adopt inclusive, critical heritage narratives and stimulate reflection.

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

Training activities could include focused workshops and guided sessions on the application of digital solutions such as podcasts, online exhibitions, and participatory storytelling tools.

Collect staff feedback

Feedback mechanisms can be strengthened by implementing structured evaluation tools for staff experiences.

Describe the experimentation session

Evaluate with real users to track the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

Evaluation sessions with students, visitors, and community groups could be planned, to test clarity, inclusivity, and accessibility.

Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)

Strengths: the digitization of colonial-era objects and the creation of the podcast represent important steps towards accessibility and wider dissemination.

Weaknesses: the objects are still presented in a static format without interactive engagement, and the descriptive criteria do not fully encourage visitors to question problematic stereotypes nor fully align with inclusivity and accessibility standards.

Opportunities: participatory practices, regional collaboration, the chance to increase national and international visibility, and the possibility to join international museum networks.

Threats: resource limitations, political sensitivities, and the risk of limited economic sustainability for these projects.

Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

Digital tools and decolonial narratives can broaden access, invite new perspectives, and encourage inclusive engagement. By making collections available online and through podcasts, the museum reaches audiences who cannot visit in person. The use of decolonial narratives in exhibitions and educational programs helps to question stereotypes and bring marginalized voices into the conversation. To strengthen this impact, the museum could implement improved digital strategies such as interactive storytelling platforms, thematic search paths within the archive, and participatory tools that allow users to contribute perspectives or annotations. Such strategies would make the digital experience more dynamic, accessible, and aligned with inclusive principles.

Conclusions

Identify technological gaps

Lack of thematic organization and participatory digital interfaces.

Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation

Managing sensitive content related to colonialism and ensuring ethical language remain complex challenges.

Delineate further lines of research

Future research should evaluate the social impact of decolonial practices, develop participatory digital paths, and improve accessibility (linguistic and cognitive).

3.5. The Castle of Gaeta: Virtual Technologies and New Public History Languages for the Storytelling and Musealization of Memory

Project Goals and Scope

This pilot project focuses on the reactivation and digital valorization of the Angioino Castle of Gaeta, a monumental site of extraordinary historical depth and architectural complexity. Located on a rocky promontory overlooking the sea, the castle has played multiple roles throughout history—from medieval fortress to Bourbon prison—and remains a powerful symbol of identity for the local community.

The initiative aims to restore meaning and accessibility to the site by applying advanced digital tools and inclusive communication strategies. Through a combination of architectural modeling, archival research, multimedia narration, and

accessibility planning, the castle becomes a case study for public history and digital heritage, rooted in a participatory and open approach to memory preservation.

This project operates within the CHANGES framework, contributing to the goals of cultural sustainability, technological innovation, and community engagement through applied research and interdisciplinary development.

Museum Typology and Initial Conditions

Classified as a Type D museum site, the Castle of Gaeta is a rich palimpsest of architectural, landscape, and intangible heritage. It encompasses two main building phases: the original 13th-century structure built by Charles of Anjou, and the later additions commissioned by Alfonso of Aragon. These were unified into a massive military fortress during the Bourbon period, eventually repurposed as a state military prison until 1990.

Before this intervention, the site lacked adequate digital documentation, interpretive tools, and accessibility pathways. Its remote location and complex morphology posed challenges for both conservation and public engagement. The project responds to this initial condition by proposing a sustainable and replicable model for reactivating such heritage spaces through digital and social innovation.

Technological Implementation and Methodology

A cornerstone of the technical intervention is the creation of an HBIM (Historic Building Information Modeling) model of the Castle of Gaeta, based on a complete exterior survey and the acquisition of the interior spaces currently open to visitors.

The process began with high-resolution photogrammetric surveys, supported by aerial ones conducted with UAV (drone) and terrestrial photogrammetric surveys using digital cameras, processed through Structure from Motion (SfM) methods to generate detailed point clouds.

This data was then used to construct a layered and parametric digital model in BIM environment, paying particular attention to the unique volumetric articulation of the castle. Open spaces like internal courtyards, architectural elements such as portals, staircases, windows, and connective passages were meticulously modeled. Special focus was placed on features that reveal historical functions, such as the surveillance towers and prison facilities.

The HBIM was integrated into a Geographic Information System (GIS) to create a multi-layered digital archive. The GIS enables georeferenced spatial analysis and

functions both as a research tool and as a WebGIS platform, currently under development, designed for remote access and digital heritage storytelling.

This dual system—HBIM and GIS—serves as a backbone for managing, conserving, and promoting the castle, linking architectural data with historical layers, multimedia content, and user interaction interfaces.

Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing

The implementation was carried out by the "Museo Facile" laboratory with the active involvement of an interdisciplinary team composed of junior and senior researchers in history, museology, multimedia production, and digital surveying. This internal collaboration was enriched by partnerships with local associations, cultural organizations, educational institutions, and community stakeholders operating in the heritage and accessibility sectors.

A central component of the initiative was the co-design process with new audiences, which involved participatory workshops, focus groups, and interactive activities aimed at integrating diverse perspectives into the reactivation of the castle. Special attention was paid to audience diversification, actively engaging students, older adults, people with disabilities, families, and tourists.

The project adopted a strong public engagement approach, treating the castle not only as a monument, but as a living platform for dialogue, memory, and innovation. The use of qualitative and quantitative tools allowed for a structured analysis of emerging audiences, enabling the project team to better understand user expectations, behavioral patterns, and preferred modes of cultural interaction.

This collaborative and inclusive framework ensured that the digital and communicative outputs reflected real social needs, supporting long-term sustainability and shared stewardship of cultural heritage.

Use of WP2/WP3 Guidelines and Prototypes

The project actively integrated and adapted the methodological framework and tools developed in WP2 and WP3 of the CHANGES program, with specific reference to the deliverable D9 – Implementation of Guidelines and Best Practices for Technology-Aided Narratives via Prototypes (v1.0). The guidelines provided a reproducible workflow for the acquisition, digitization, and semantic storytelling of cultural heritage, which were critically applied and contextualized within the complex site of the Castle of Gaeta.

Following the principles of transparency, reusability, and interoperability, the project team implemented a structured process for 3D digitization based on Structure from Motion (SfM) photogrammetry and UAV surveys. These practices closely aligned with D9's recommendations for efficient 3D acquisition and data management workflows, especially in contexts where budget and environmental conditions constrain traditional scanning systems.

The pilot also embraced the WP3 emphasis on open formats and FAIR data practices, opting for interoperable outputs (e.g., OBJ, FBX) and metadata integration strategies inspired by the Story Ontology framework. The integration of HBIM and GIS systems reflects the methodological synergy between story-centric and space-centric approaches, as described in the guidelines for immersive and site-specific narratives.

Several D9 prototypes and strategies were tested or adapted, including:

- WebXR and 360° immersive storytelling: the HBIM-GIS system enabled spatial navigation enriched by multimedia content, echoing the Other Renaissance digital twin approach for remote exhibitions.
- Accessible smart object design: tactile and haptic models were developed using methods consistent with the Florence Smart Prototyping Guidelines, particularly for blind and visually impaired users.
- Narrative scaffolding and modular storytelling structures: thematic routes through the castle applied the D9 guidance on progressive and thematic narrative models, incorporating both chronological sequences and micro-narratives (e.g., the Bourbon prison experience).

The project also addressed D9's call for inclusive participatory design by conducting field-testing with diverse user groups. The feedback loop directly supported refinement of user interfaces, narrative density, and multimodal access, particularly in line with Sections 5.2 (Real-Time Site-Specific Narrative Approaches) and 5.4 (Narrative Structures) of the WP3 documentation.

Furthermore, by documenting the full acquisition and storytelling process, including metadata enrichment and user pathway logging, the project aligned with the CHANGES reproducibility mandate (see D9, Section 4.1-4.5), supporting future Social Digital Twin (SDT) development and long-term methodological scalability.

Through this process, the project contributed empirical feedback to the broader CHANGES ecosystem and reinforced the value of designing digital narratives as open, modular, and co-authored frameworks.

Digitalization and Interface Design

A key element of the digital strategy was the attention to inclusive and multimodal access. All digital content—models, maps, multimedia narrations—was developed with user experience and cognitive accessibility in mind.

Significantly, multimedia products were created in Italian, English, Italian Sign Language (LIS), and International Sign (IS). This choice reflects a commitment not only to linguistic pluralism, but to genuine inclusion of Deaf communities at both national and international levels.

Sign languages are not auxiliary translations; they are full linguistic systems that bring unique spatial and gestural richness to the storytelling of cultural heritage. Their presence allows for a multimodal engagement with architecture, especially meaningful in sites like Gaeta, where spatial relationships carry historical significance. Including LIS and IS affirms the agency of deaf individuals as cultural participants, not passive recipients.

In addition to signed videos, the project includes tactile models with haptic feedback, Braille materials, and audio-guided tours, reflecting a commitment to “accessibility by design.”

Participatory testing with user groups—students, elderly visitors, visually and hearing-impaired persons—played a key role in shaping the final outputs.

Staff Training and Community Engagement

Dedicated training modules were developed for staff and collaborators, covering technical tools (SfM, BIM, GIS), digital storytelling, and inclusive design. These sessions ensured capacity-building for long-term site management and content updates.

The project also prioritized outreach to the local community through guided tours, workshops, and public events that reframed the castle not as a closed monument, but as a shared memory space and cultural catalyst.

Evaluation and Experimentation

User testing revealed the potential of the developed tools to foster emotional and intellectual engagement with the site. The use of augmented reality, narrative paths, and digital mapping effectively reinforced the historical narrative and increased visitor satisfaction.

A SWOT analysis confirmed:

- Strengths: interdisciplinary methodology, accessibility, participatory framework;

- Weaknesses: technological infrastructure limitations;
- Opportunities: educational integration, tourism development, internationalization;
- Threats: funding continuity and digital obsolescence.

Public Output and Dissemination

The project generated two key multimedia outputs that are publicly accessible:

- Il Castello di Gaeta tra memoria e innovazione – [Watch](#)
- Il Castello angioino: un viaggio nella memoria – [Watch](#)

Dissemination was not considered a secondary activity, but rather a core element of the project's mission. Through public events, presentations, and immersive experiences, the team activated a dialogue between research, community memory, and digital innovation.

Past Events:

- CHANGES Conference – Gaeta, October 10–11, 2024 – A major two-day public event that brought together scholars, digital heritage professionals, local administrators, and citizens, focusing on cultural participation and digital transformation. [Event press review and website](#)
- Poster Presentation – “Patrimonio culturale al futuro” Conference, Roma Tre, January 23–24, 2025 – The project's first research results were presented as part of the national conference Cultural Heritage to the Future: Social Sustainability, Technological Innovation, and Digital Transformation, held at the Aula Magna of the Faculty of Letters, Roma Tre University, Rome. The event was part of a national strategy for the dissemination of results from the CHANGES PE20 program.

Upcoming Events:

- Digital Heritage 2025 International Conference – Poster Presentation. Location: University of Siena, September 8–12, 2025. As part of the prestigious international conference Digital Heritage 2025, the project will be represented by the poster entitled: “Digital Technologies for the Conservation and Enhancement of the Castle of Gaeta: An Inclusive and Participatory Approach”, authored by Ivana Bruno, Luca Bianchi, Paolo Leonini, Marta Salvatore, Laura Saturnino, and Luca Spatola. The poster highlights the methodological innovations and accessibility strategies adopted in the project, with special attention to digital storytelling, WebGIS integration, and public engagement practices. Its inclusion in the official program confirms the project's relevance and contribution to international discussions on digital heritage, accessibility, and co-designed cultural narratives.

Fondazione CHANGES – Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society

- European Researchers' Night – STREETS, September 25, 2025. Location: Castello Angioino di Gaeta – 9:00–13:00.
- Award, Training, and Research: Opportunities from the DTC Lazio Excellence Center This institutional event, hosted by UNICAS in collaboration with SCIRE and DTC Lazio, will present new calls for co-financed R&D and training projects. It will also feature an "Award" section for best theses in cultural technologies. Speakers include:
 - Ivana Bruno, Rector's Delegate for the Dissemination of Culture – SCIRE
 - Simone Bozzato, President of the COE, Center of Excellence DTC Lazio
- Immersive Experience – LUOGHI, VOCI E STORIE, September 23, 2025. Location: Castello Angioino di Gaeta – 9:00–13:00 This hybrid sensory tour retraces the experience of the castle during its time as a military prison (until June 30, 1990). Visitors will walk through the first- and second-floor "Camerata A" and the Piedmontese Cells, transformed into narrative spaces through direct testimonies and immersive storytelling. The event is curated by Ivana Bruno, with participation from researchers at the DTC Lazio CdE and UNICAS "Museo Facile" Lab, including Luca Bianchi, Paolo Leonini, Laura Saturnino, Marta Salvatore, and Luca Spatola.

Conclusions and Future Directions

The results achieved demonstrate the transformative power of digital tools when combined with an inclusive and community-centered approach to heritage. However, they also highlight the need for structured methodology and long-term frameworks.

The next phase will focus on:

- Publishing open-access guidelines based on the methods and tools developed;
- Expanding the digital library, applying universal design criteria;
- Testing new digital services, tailored to broader audiences through participatory design.

A major future direction is the development of a Social Digital Twin (SDT) of the castle, integrating its physical architecture with social memory, user contributions, and collective narratives. This will involve:

- Thick mapping of archival and citizen-sourced data;
- AI-driven visitor analysis;
- Integration of underground mapping with immersive exploration;

- Thematic storytelling based on local mythology (e.g. Ulysses).

The SDT will be supported by an innovation lab format, engaging institutions, enterprises, associations, and active citizens in co-designing sustainable strategies.

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